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Abstract

Despite sustained political pressure to increase migrant returns, European Union (EU) countries enforce only around 20% of return orders, raising key questions about what drives return enforcement. While institutional and legal explanations dominate existing research, enforcement outcomes vary widely even among countries with similar policy frameworks. To explain such variation, we develop a theoretical framework that bridges rationalist approaches emphasizing external incentives with constructivist approaches focusing on socialization and alignment. Our comprehensive cross-national analysis focuses on enforced returns from 28 EU countries to non-EU states (2009-2024), based on nearly 50,000 dyadic observations and Pseudo Poisson Maximum Likelihood models. We additionally analyze 20,000 observations distinguishing between forced and voluntary/incentivized returns (2014-2023) to uncover modality-specific patterns. We assess the influence of administrative capacity, interstate relations, historical ties, and domestic political-economic conditions on return outcomes. We find that embassy presence, government effectiveness, colonial ties, and Schengen visa waivers are robust predictors of higher return rates. In contrast, formal readmission agreements and leverage tools such as aid and trade show limited effects. Some of these factors operate differently across return modalities: destination-country's government effectiveness predicts more forced returns while origin-country effectiveness predicts more voluntary/incentivized returns. Visa waivers are associated with more voluntary/incentivized returns. These findings challenge dominant policy assumptions and underscore the role of long-term bilateral relationships and sociocultural embeddedness in shaping return enforcement across the EU.

Introduction

Unauthorized cross-border migration has become a central political and policy concern of governments across the Global North. Increasingly, these governments seek not only to prevent irregular entry but also to enforce the removal of individuals who lack legal authorization to remain. In the European Union (EU), political leaders have repeatedly emphasized the need to increase returns. In 2023, then-German Chancellor Olaf Scholz vowed to deport migrations “more often and faster,” echoing French President Emmanuel Macron’s 2019 call to expel “all the people who have nothing to do here [in France]” (Hickmann & Kurbjuweit, 2023; Pascual, 2022). Such rhetoric reflects mounting political pressure to demonstrate control over migration and uphold the integrity of asylum systems by enforcing returns of unauthorized migrants.

Despite this urgency as framed by politicians, actual return enforcement remains limited. Of the 453,380 orders to leave (OTLs) issued by EU member states in 2024, about a quarter (110,385) resulted in actual returns (Eurostat, 2025c, 2025b). This persistent gap between policy ambition and enforcement outcomes raises a fundamental question: what determines the success or failure of return enforcement?

Existing research has pointed to destination country’s interest and capacity as key factors underlying return enforcement (Anderson et al., 2011). However, such explanations cannot fully explain the striking variation in enforcement across destination-origin country pairs. Consider the example of Germany: It achieved over 50% return rates with China annually in 2008-2019 despite having no readmission agreement, while return rates to Vietnam decreased from 45% to 15% in the same period even with a bilateral readmission agreement in effect since 1995 (Eurostat, 2025c, 2025b).

More recent studies have turned to bilateral political and economic relations to explain return outcomes (Kefale et al., 2025; Marie Borrelli & Lindberg, 2025; Stutz, 2025). Most studies rely on single-country case studies that cannot capture systematic cross-national patterns. To address this limitation, we synthesize rationalist approaches emphasizing external incentives with constructivist approaches into socialization and alignment. This integrated framework enables us to assess return enforcement as a relational outcome emerging from both cost-benefit calculation and normative alignment between states, extending the narrow institutional analyses that have dominated the field.

This study analyzes two datasets: (1) nearly 50,000 dyadic observations of total returns from 28 EU countries to non-EU states in 2009-2024 and (2) about 20,000 observations of return modality breakdown between forced and voluntary returns in 2014-2023. We develop an integrated theoretical framework that brings together administrative capacity, interstate leverage and alignment, domestic political-economic pressures, and sociocultural ties. Empirically, we apply Pseudo Poisson Maximum Likelihood regression models to Eurostat's Enforcement of Immigration Legislation data, incorporating multiple fixed-effects specifications to isolate the effects of time-varying bilateral characteristics.

Our findings challenge conventional policy assumptions. While administrative capacity – measured through government effectiveness and embassy presence – emerges as a strong predictor of returns, formal readmission agreements exert only marginal effects. Similarly, domestic economic or political pressures in either origin or destination countries show weak or inconsistent associations with return enforcement. Instead, long-standing bilateral factors, such

as colonial ties, political alignment in UN voting and visa liberalization arrangements, play a far more substantial role.

By moving beyond institutional and legalist approaches, this paper contributes to a growing body of research that sees return enforcement not merely as a function of state capacity or coercive instruments, but as embedded in broader geopolitical, historical, and sociocultural relationships. In doing so, we offer new empirical insights and policy implications for the EU's evolving return and readmission architecture.

Return Enforcement and Cooperation: State of Literature and Conceptual Framework

From State Capacity to Bilateral Dynamics

Initial scholarship on return enforcement emphasized the role of destination countries' institutional capacity, particularly their legislative and bureaucratic abilities, to translate migration policy mandates into action. Ellermann (2005, 2009) conceptualized deportation as a form of coercive capacity, arguing that variation in enforcement outcomes stems primarily from the destination country's legal and administrative institutions. However, this approach struggles to explain empirical inconsistencies on why, for example, countries with similar legal and institutional setups achieve vastly different return outcomes across origin states.

Recent studies have responded by broadening the scope of the analysis. Scholars emphasize the bilateral nature of return enforcement, reframing it as a process contingent on cooperation between origin and destination countries (Sinnige et al., 2025; Torres Chedraui et al., 2025). Within this framework, the effectiveness of formal instruments such as readmission agreements is understood to be embedded in broader interstate relations.

Readmission agreements are often regarded as the cornerstone of EU return policy, designed to provide a legal framework for the identification and return of irregular migrants (Carrera, 2016). Yet their effectiveness remains disputed. Some studies find that such agreements lead to increased returns, but the effects tend to be modest, temporary, or conditional on other factors like accession aspirations among Eastern European and Western Balkan states (Stutz & Trauner, 2022). Using Eurostat data, Torres Chedraui et al. (2025) demonstrate that bilateral agreements tend to be more effective than EU-wide ones but still yield only marginal gains. These findings suggest that formal agreements alone are insufficient to drive sustained cooperation.

Case studies further highlight the fragility of these frameworks. Norway, a country with “strong enforcement interests with extensive enforcement capacities” (Leerkes & van Houte, 2020, p. 330), saw a brief increase in returns following a readmission agreement with Iraq in 2009, only for cooperation to decline after 2011 despite the agreement remaining in force (Janmyr, 2016). Similarly, Norway’s memorandum of understanding with Ethiopia failed to produce consistent enforcement results (Kefale et al., 2025). These patterns underscore that readmission frameworks may lack the durability or coercive force that policymakers assume, particularly in the absence of sustained political will.

Incentives and Socialization: Competing Logics of Cooperation

To explain the extent to which countries of origin comply with return requests, two theoretical models have gained prominence. The *external incentive model*, rooted in rationalist bargaining theory, posits that states cooperate when material benefits (e.g., development aid,

trade concessions, visa facilitation) outweigh domestic political and economic costs of accepting returnees (McGregor et al., 2025; Schimmelfennig & Sedelmeier, 2020). These costs can include lost remittances, strained public services, and domestic backlash against perceived foreign imposition (Adam et al., 2020; Mouthaan, 2019).

Yet empirical patterns often defy this cost-benefit logic. According to Stutz (2025), India and Senegal, which are considered democracies with strong diaspora networks, demonstrate limited cooperation despite economic interdependence with the EU. In contrast, states with few incentives or high domestic costs, such as Kenya and Lebanon, have relatively higher return rates with the EU (Stutz, 2025). These anomalies suggest that material incentives alone cannot fully explain cooperation patterns.

A second model, drawing from sociological institutionalism, emphasizes social learning and norm diffusion (Bearce & Bondanella, 2007; Torres Chedraui et al., 2025). Here, cooperation is seen as the outcome of socialization processes, in which states internalize norms through repeated interactions and adapt their behavior to align with international expectations or shared identities. Countries seeking closer political alignment with the EU, such as those in the European Neighbourhood Policy-East, may comply with return requests to signal legitimacy and commitment to European norms even in the absence of immediate material gains (Stutz, 2023).

These models are not mutually exclusive. In practice, cooperation likely depends on a combination of instrumental incentives and normative alignment. However, empirical research has insufficiently accounted for the interaction between these mechanisms or to systematically test them using comparative data. Moreover, few studies integrate dyadic characteristics, focusing instead on either the sending or receiving country in isolation.

Domestic Pressures: Political Economy and Public Opinion

A third strand of literature explores the influence of domestic political and economic pressures on return enforcement.

In destination countries, scholars have explored whether enforcement intensity is linked to economic cycles, electoral dynamics, or public attitudes toward immigration. In a panel study of 25 OECD countries from 2000 and 2009, Wong (2015) found that deportations per total population increased with far-right party strength and rising asylum claims, while macroeconomic indicators such as GDP growth and unemployment yield inconsistent results. Even within destination countries, the effects of public opinion, party politics, and administrative backlogs remain inconclusive. For example, Hatton (2021) shows that public salience of immigration does not always translate into policy outcomes, while far-right electoral success may increase rhetorical pressure without altering enforcement practice. However, these analyses focused solely on destination-country factors, neglecting the cooperative nature of enforcement, which also depends on origin countries' willingness and capacity to accept returnees.

Origin states often resist returns due to their own domestic constraints. The loss of remittances – an essential income stream for many Global South economies – can reduce incentives to cooperate, particularly when high unemployment or political instability may reduce governments' ability to absorb returnees (Mouthaan, 2019). Political costs are also salient: public opposition, especially where returnees are viewed as unfairly targeted by Global North governments, can discourage cooperation (Cham & Adam, 2023). In some cases, returning individuals face harassment, discrimination, or re-migration pressures, undermining the

legitimacy of the process (Schuster & Majidi, 2015). Governments must also devote resources to reintegrate returnees, who often arrive abruptly after deportation with limited preparation or support, but the reintegration assistance is inconsistently provided or poorly coordinated (Scalettaris & Gubert, 2019). These logistical and financial burdens can overwhelm local infrastructure and generate additional political risks for origin country governments. The Gambia is an example: following its 2016 democratic transition, the new government initially cooperated with EU return efforts but imposed a moratorium in 2019 under domestic pressure, prompting EU visa restrictions in response (Cham & Adam, 2023, 2025).

Against these costs, destination states in the EU deploy various incentives to secure cooperation. The EU's 2016 agreement with Turkey illustrates the strategic bargaining: visa facilitation, renewed accession negotiations, and financial aid were sufficient to elicit Ankara's compliance with return arrangements despite substantial domestic costs (Demiryontar, 2021). Similarly, countries within the European Neighborhood Policy-East have cooperated consistently with the EU on return and readmission, driven in part by credible prospects for visa liberalization or eventual EU accession (Stutz, 2023).

Regime type may also influence cooperation patterns. Stutz and Trauner (2025) analyze the relationship between political systems and return outcomes and find a positive correlation between democratic governance (measured by Freedom House scores) and higher EU-wide return rates. Yet this relationship is not deterministic: there are democracies with low enforcement (e.g., India, Senegal) and autocracies with high return enforcement (e.g., Russia) (Stutz & Trauner, 2025). Such outliers suggest that regime type interacts with, rather than

determines, states' willingness to cooperate, reinforcing the need to consider both incentives and normative alignment.

Beyond Formal Policy: Historical and Sociocultural Linkages

An emerging line of research points to the role of sociocultural and historical ties in shaping return enforcement. Colonial legacies, common languages, and transnational communities can influence bilateral cooperation in complex ways. Shared institutional or legal systems may facilitate coordination, while historical grievances and ongoing disagreement may impede it. Origin countries may see return enforcement, especially deportation, as a form of neocolonialism and thus challenge the legitimacy of return (Cham & Adam, 2025; Majidi et al., 2024). In the case of Moroccan-French bilateral relation, Qadim (2014) showed that Morocco's officials contested France's practices in migration control. The contestation was most pronounced in forced return, which Moroccan officials see as undermining their nation's "sovereignty, credibility and dignity at the international level" (p. 256).

Migrant diaspora populations, for instance, play a multifaceted role in influencing return outcomes. Diaspora networks can facilitate irregular stay by providing migrants with information, housing, and informal employment (Engbersen et al., 2006). Diaspora members can also act as gatekeepers to exclude irregular migrants (Sha, 2021) when established migrants perceive irregular arrivals as threatening their hard-won social status. Therefore, diaspora communities may mobilize in opposite directions: some members may organize to resist deportations through legal aid and protests, while others may support stricter enforcement.

The Need for a Systematic Dyadic Approach and Integrated Framework

Despite increasing scholarly attention to return migration enforcement, most existing studies rely on either destination-country characteristics or single-country case analyses. As a result, the bilateral and relational nature of return enforcement remains poorly understood. Yet return cooperation is inherently dyadic: it requires the willingness and capacity of EU destination countries to remove unauthorized migrants, the willingness and capacity of origin countries to accept them, and bilateral relationship that facilitates the countries to cooperate. A systematic, dyadic approach allows us to model both sides of this equation and account for how structural and relational factors interact across country pairs.

To explain variation in enforced return outcomes, we propose an integrated framework that brings together four domains of explanatory variables: (1) return and readmission capacities, (2) interstate relations and leverage, (3) domestic political-economic pressures, and (4) historical and sociocultural linkages. While partially overlap, each domain draws from a distinct strand of literature and reflects a different mechanism by which return enforcement is shaped (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework for Explaining Enforced Return Outcomes

First, return and readmission capacities refer to the institutional and administrative tools that states possess to implement return decisions. These include the quality of governance, the presence of functioning embassies, the availability of legal frameworks such as readmission agreements, and safe country designations. While such frameworks are often assumed to guarantee cooperation, their effectiveness depends on both countries' ability to operationalize them in practice. We hypothesize that higher return and readmission capacities in both origin and destination countries are associated with more enforced returns (H1).

Second, interstate relations and leverage capture the broader political and economic dependencies that influence return cooperation. We distinguish two mechanisms: Economic

leverage reflects material dependencies through bilateral aid flows and trade volumes, while policy leverage through Schengen visa waiver facilitates regular mobility. Following the “external incentive” logic, origin countries may accept returns in exchange for maintaining these benefits. Political alignment, measured through UN voting similarity and shared institutional frameworks (proxied by EU candidacy status), captures normative convergence and shared political orientations. While EU candidacy involves material gains, the candidate countries are committed to deeper political integration and norm alignment. Considering the current study’s exploratory nature, we combine these in H2: Greater economic and policy leverage and political alignment between states are associated with higher return enforcement. However, we acknowledge that this hypothesis combines distinct mechanisms: leverage through cost-benefit bargaining versus alignment through socialization and shared norms.

Third, domestic political and economic conditions affect the calculus of return in both destination and origin countries. In origin countries, reliance on remittances, high unemployment, or authoritarian governance may reduce the political will or legitimacy to accept returnees. In destination countries, public opinion, electoral incentives, and administrative backlogs may shape whether and how return enforcement is pursued. These factors reflect how domestic constraints and pressures mediate migration governance decisions. We hypothesize that for destination countries, greater domestic political and economic pressures are associated with higher return enforcement across dyads; For origin countries, the reverse relationship holds (H3).

Fourth, historical and sociocultural ties influence cooperation by shaping trust, administrative compatibility, and diplomatic norms. Colonial legacies may foster shared legal systems and bureaucratic procedures but may also generate postcolonial resentment in origin

countries (Qadim, 2014). Common language can reduce barriers in documentation and verification processes. Migrant diaspora populations play a complex role: They may support irregular migrants and mobilize against enforcement; Yet in some instances, they may act as gatekeepers who support enforcement (Sha, 2021). These elements reflect a longer historical arc of interaction between states and societies. We hypothesize that closer historical and sociocultural ties between countries are associated with higher return outcomes (H4).

Taken together, this framework bridges rationalist and constructivist approaches to international cooperation. It integrates material incentives, institutional capacities, and socially embedded relationships into a single explanatory model. By testing these hypotheses using dyadic observations and a set of high-dimensional fixed effects, we aim to identify not just correlates, but systematic patterns in how return enforcement unfolds across the EU countries' external relations.

Empirical Analysis

To identify the structural and relational determinants of enforced return outcomes, we estimate a series of dyadic panel models using Pseudo Poisson Maximum Likelihood regression. This approach is well suited to modelling skewed count data with an excess of zeros and addressing heteroskedasticity concerns common in migration flows datasets.

Model Specification

Our dependent variable is the (log-transformed) count of enforced returns between each EU-third country dyad and year (R_{ijt}). To capture both structural and temporal variation, we estimate the following fixed-effects panel model:

$$\begin{aligned} \log(R_{ijt} + 1) = & \alpha + \beta_1 \text{Agreement}_{ijt} + \beta_2 \text{Capacity}_{ijt} + \beta_3 \text{InterRelat}_{ijt} \\ & + \beta_4 \text{PolEconPres}_{ijt} + \beta_5 \text{HistTies}_{ijt} + \mu_{ij} + \tau_t + \varepsilon_{ijt} \end{aligned}$$

- Where: Agreement_{ijt} : Indicates presence of formal return-related agreements (e.g., readmission treaties).
- Capacity_{ijt} : Captures administrative capacity, including government effectiveness, embassy presence, and return policy tools (e.g. safe country designations).
- $\text{InterRelation}_{ijt}$: Reflects bilateral political and economic ties (e.g., aid, trade, UN voting alignment, visa waivers).
- $\text{PolEconPresssure}_{ijt}$: Measures domestic political and economic pressures in both EU- and third-country.
- HistTies_{ij} : Encodes historical and sociocultural linkages such as colonial ties, common language, and diaspora presence.
- μ_{ij} : Dyadic fixed effects.
- τ_t : Year fixed effects.
- ε_{ijt} : Error term.

We include lagged and contemporaneous values of orders to leave (OTLs) – also log-transformed – to account for return issuance volumes in the absence of individual-level cohort linkages.

Data Sources and Variable Construction

The analysis relies on two datasets. The primary panel spans 49,877 EU-third country dyad-years from 2009 to 2024, with enforced return data drawn from Eurostat’s annual “Orders to leave” and “Returned Following an Order to Leave” series (Eurostat, 2025c, 2025b). Here, “enforced return” refers to “situations where individuals are compelled to leave the country due to the actions and presence of the state” (Torres Chedraui et al., 2024, p. 9). A secondary panel (2014-2023 with 20,699 observations) includes data disaggregated by modality of forced and voluntary/incentivized from Eurostat (2025d). The dataset’s voluntary return category includes both assisted voluntary return and reintegration (AVRR) and recorded unassisted voluntary departure. We use the term “voluntary/incentivized” to emphasize that (1) these two kinds of return are not distinguished, and (2) the so-called “voluntary return” is not purely out of individuals’ willingness, but is often a result of state presence and persuasion (Torres Chedraui et al., 2024).

The Enforcement of Immigration Legislation (EIL) dataset has several important limitations that constrain its analytical utility (Belmonte et al., 2021; Maliepaard et al., 2022). Prior to 2014, the data did not differentiate among return modalities of forced removals, assisted voluntary returns, and unassisted voluntary returns; Nor did it indicate whether returns were to countries of origin or to transit countries. Although disaggregation by return type was introduced

beginning in 2014, reporting remained inconsistent and limited to a subset of EU member states. A major improvement occurred in 2021, when revised EU regulations mandated quarterly reporting by all member states, with standardized breakdowns by return type, assistance received, and destination country (Eurostat, 2024).

Nonetheless, key limitations persist. First, the absence of cohort identifiers makes it impossible to link return events directly to specific orders to leave (OTLs). Second, numbers are rounded to the nearest 5, which introduces measurement error. Third, OTL issuance and enforcement practices vary widely across countries due to divergent legal frameworks, administrative procedures, and reporting standards, further reducing cross-country comparability (Maliepaard et al., 2022). Despite these challenges, the EIL database remains the most comprehensive and standardized source currently available for analyzing return enforcement outcomes across the European Union.

On the explanatory side we have incorporated the following variable categories into our analysis:

Administrative Capacity:

- *Government effectiveness*: World Bank's World Governance Indicators, a continuous index with -2.5 as lowest and 2.5 as highest (Kaufmann & Kraay, 2024), following recent studies (e.g., Van Wolleghem & Sicakkan, 2023).
- *Embassy presence*: Diplometrics database (Moyer et al., 2021).
- *Policy tools*: Bilateral readmission agreements (Cassarino, 2024), safe country designations (Guichard & Machado, 2025), which we complemented with the changes in most recent years. All these policy variables are measured as binary (0/1) indicators.

Interstate Relations and Leverage:

- *Aid*: Log of bilateral aid (ODA) disbursements per year (DAC2A: OECD (2025)).
- *Trade*: Log of third country export to EU country per dyad per year (CEPII BACI dataset, Gaulier & Zignago (2010)).
- *Political alignment*: Based on UN General Assembly voting similarity (Voeten et al., 2024), we calculated each country dyad's absolute distance between voting records' ideal point estimates with larger value indicating higher disagreement.
- *Visa access, and EU candidacy*: Visa free access according to "Visa waiver agreements" on EUR-Lex (2023). EU accession candidacy status from Eurostat's candidate country listings (Eurostat, n.d.).

Domestic Political-Economic Pressures:

- *Economic Indicators*: GDP growth and unemployment rates in World Development Indicators (World Bank, 2025)
- *Asylum Pressure*: Log-transformed first-instance applications (Eurostat, 2025a).
- *Public salience*: For EU domestic politics, we use Eurobarometer data (European Commission, 2025) to calculate the proportion of respondents who selected "immigration" as one of the two most important issues facing their country, following Hatton (2021).
- *Far-right party strength*: Share of parliamentary seats (Döring & Manow, 2024).

Historical and Sociocultural Linkages:

- *Colonial past and common language*: CEPII Gravity dataset binary coded; (Conte et al., 2022).

- *Diaspora size*: Bilateral migrant stocks log-transformed (Standaert & Rayp, 2025).

Missing Data Treatment

We apply conservative imputation protocols:

- For strictly positive flow variables (aid, trade), missing values are imputed as zero.
- For gradually evolving variables (e.g., migrant stocks, embassy presence), the latest available observations are carried forward.
- Time-invariant characteristics retain fixed values within the dyads.
- Remaining missing cases underwent listwise deletion.

Estimation Strategy

Our identification strategy relies on a sequence of four progressively restrictive model specifications, each employing increasingly saturated fixed effects to isolate causal patterns in return enforcement.

In the aggregate return analysis, *Model 1* serves as the baseline specification, incorporating year fixed effects to account for common temporal shocks (such as COVID-19 pandemic) that simultaneously affect all dyads. This model includes the full set of origin-, destination-, and dyad-level covariates, allowing for the examination of cross-sectional variation while controlling for shared time trends.

Model 2 adds origin-year and destination-year fixed effects, which absorb time-varying country-specific factors (e.g., economic shocks, political shifts) that might otherwise confound

bilateral relationships. This setup focuses the estimation on within-country variation over time rather than between-country differences.

Model 3 introduces dyad fixed effects and retains origin-year fixed effects, thereby controlling for all time-invariant characteristics of each country pair, including geographic proximity, colonial ties, and legal traditions. This restrictive specification allows us to isolate the effect of destination-country temporal variation on return outcomes within stable bilateral relationships.

Conversely, *Model 4* includes dyad and destination-year fixed effects, while retaining origin-country covariates. This structure enables the identification of how time-varying conditions in origin countries influence return enforcement, holding bilateral and destination-specific variation constant.

For the return modality analysis (forced vs. voluntary/incentivized), we follow a parallel strategy. Model A provides a baseline with covariates and year-fixed effects. Models B-D sequentially introduced dyad-year and country-year fixed effects to isolate variation attributable to origin- or destination-side dynamics, while distinguishing the distinct drivers of each return type.

Descriptive Trends in Return Enforcement

Figure 2 displays EU-wide trends in return enforcement from 2008 to 2024. The number of orders to leave (OTLs) issued annually declined from approximately 600,000 in 2008 to around 450,000 by 2024. Notably, the COVID-19 pandemic caused a sharp temporary decline during 2020-2021. However, the EIL dataset does not capture how many of these orders were appealed or revoked, and it largely underreports non-assisted voluntary return (Maliepaard et al., 2022).

Figure 2 Third-country nationals ordered to leave, and those returned following an order to leave, EU aggregate. Source: Eurostat (2025b, 2025a)

Actual returns to third countries¹ followed a similarly downward trajectory but at significantly lower levels, dropping from roughly 220,000 in 2008 to about 110,000 in 2024. The persistent and substantial gap between OTLs and enforced returns underscores the core enforcement challenge examined in this study.

Figure 3 Dyadic enforced return rate by year. Source: Eurostat (2025b, 2025a)

¹ The difference between “total return” and “return to third countries” were the returns redirected to other EU countries (e.g., under bilateral arrangements unrelated to the Dublin Regulation)

Figure 3 presents year-by-year boxplots of dyadic (unweighted) return rates across all EU-third country pairs. Each boxplot represents the distribution of return rates for all country pairs in that year, with the box showing the interquartile range (25th to 75th percentile) and the horizontal line marking the median. In 2023, for example, the median return rate was about 25%, meaning half of all EU-third country pairs had return rates below this threshold. However, the interquartile range extended from near 0% to over 60%, implying that while some dyads achieve minimal returns, others enforce most of their orders. Across all years, there are outliers exceeding 100% return rate which appear as dots above the 1.0 mark on the y-axis. These seemingly impossible rates (more returns than orders issued) expose a fundamental limitation in the data structure: the lack of cohort identifiers that would link specific returns to their orders to leave. Consequently, individuals ordered to leave in late 2022 but returned in early 2023 would be counted against 2023's orders, artificially inflating that year's return rate. This temporal mismatch is pronounced for dyads with small numbers of orders, where even a few delayed returns can hugely distort return rate.

Figure 4 Dyadic enforced return rate by EU country. Source: Eurostat (2025b, 2025a)

Figure 4 disaggregates return rates by EU destination country. Some countries, particularly those in Northern Europe (Denmark, Finland, Sweden), achieve median return rates of 50% and higher. Others like Belgium and Italy average closer to 20%. This divergent pattern aligns with scholarship on “variation in post-arrival enforcement policies and their underlying interests and capacities,” as demonstrated by Leerkes and van Houte (2020, p. 319). Moreover, wide interquartile ranges reveal that return outcomes differ substantially by origin country, even within the same EU member state. For example, Germany shows a median return rate 35.5%, but its interquartile range spans from approximately 8.3% to 72.9%, with outliers reaching both zero and above 100%. In other words, Germany might achieve over 70% return rates with some origin countries while barely managing 10% with others. The cross- and within-country heterogeneities suggest that enforcement variation cannot be attributed solely to administrative capacity and instead reflect dyad-specific relational dynamics.

These visualizations also highlight the limitations of aggregate return rates as a performance metric. Variations may reflect not only enforcement effort and capacity, but also migrant composition, national practices around OTL issuance, legal safeguards, and data reporting standards (Maliepaard et al., 2022). For instance, states that issue OTLs selectively to individuals with high deportability may exhibit artificially high return rates despite low absolute numbers. These concerns reinforce our decision to focus on *return counts*, coupled with fixed effects, to better capture dyadic enforcement dynamics while mitigating measurement biases.

Data Description

Our analysis draws on two complementary datasets. Summary statistics are provided in Tables A1a and A1b (Appendix).

The primary dataset covers enforced returns between 28 EU member states and third countries from 2009 to 2024, yielding 49,877 dyad-year observations after applying missing data treatments. While this dataset provides comprehensive coverage, it does not distinguish between return modalities: forced removal (deportation) versus voluntary/incentivized return.

To address this limitation, we use a secondary dataset (2014-2023) that disaggregates returns by these two modalities for 23 EU countries. This dataset contains 20,699 dyad-years but has restricted temporal and geographic coverage. Key absences include Cyprus, Finland, Lithuania, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom, as well as nearly all years for Germany (except 2018). The exclusion of both major and smaller destination countries introduces potential selection bias, particularly in analyses of how administrative capacity influences return type.

Both datasets display extreme right-skew and clustering, which implies the high concentration of returns within a small subset of bilateral corridors. The aggregate data's annual return count per dyad has a mean of 40.3 while the median is zero. Orders to leave show a similar pattern, averaging 120.9 per dyad-year, again with a median of zero. In the modality dataset, average annual dyadic returns are nearly equal for forced (12.6) and voluntary/incentivized returns (13.9) returns, though the medians remain zero for both.

Results

Tables 2a and 2b present full regression estimates, while Figures 5a and 5b visualize coefficient plots for the baseline models using aggregate and disaggregated return data, respectively.

Return and Readmission Capacity

Diplomatic presence is a robust and consistent predictor of return outcomes, strongly supporting *Hypothesis 1*. The presence of a third-country embassy in an EU country is associated with a 32% increase in total returns (Model 1 in aggregate return analysis), including 24.5% more forced returns and 43.5% more voluntary/incentivized return (Model A in return modality analysis). Embassy presence in the reverse direction – from EU country to third country – also shows positive effects: 21.4% more total returns (Model 1), 14.5% more forced returns and 12.7% more voluntary/incentivized returns (Model A). These effects remain stable across fixed-effect specifications, indicating that diplomatic infrastructure plays a critical role in return administration.

Government effectiveness also matters, though less consistently. A one standard-deviation increase in destination-country governance effectiveness (0.6 points) is associated with an 11.8% rise in total returns and a 22.9% rise in forced returns. In contrast, a similar increase in origin-country effectiveness (0.9 points) predicts only 6.6% more total returns (Model 2) and 14.3% more voluntary/incentivized returns (Model A), suggesting that origin-side capacity facilitates non coercive return mechanisms.

By contrast, return policy instruments such as readmission agreements show weak or inconsistent effects. Agreements are associated with a small and statistically insignificant 2-4% increase in total returns (Models 1 and 2). In disaggregated return modality analysis, they are linked to an 18.8% rise in forced returns (Model A), though this effect disappears with dyad fixed effects (Model B). These modest effects suggest that formal agreements alone do not drive enforcement outcomes.

The designation of a country as safe yields no consistent pattern. In aggregate models, it correlates negatively with total returns (Models 1-2), possibly due to irregular stay incentives after asylum rejection (Atak, 2018). However, in return modality analysis, the designation as a safe origin or third country is weakly associated with higher forced returns (5.6% in Model A), and 12.6% higher voluntary/incentivized returns (Model B).

Interstate Relations and Leverage

Among indicators of bilateral leverage, the Schengen visa waiver strongly supports *Hypothesis 2*. Visa-free third countries, i.e., nationalities, are associated with 7-10% higher total returns across specifications (Models 1 and 3), and especially higher voluntary returns: 15.8% in

Model A and 29.7% in Model C. This points to the relevance of mobility regimes in facilitating cooperative returns.

Political alignment measured via UN voting similarity has mixed effects. Greater divergence in UN votes predicts 5-18% fewer returns in aggregate models, with stronger effects in more saturated specifications. Yet in modality-specific models, political misalignment corresponds to lower voluntary returns but higher forced returns, though not always statistically significant. This pattern possibly reflects two mechanisms: First, political affinity may influence the modality rather than the likelihood of return cooperation. Second, countries with closer political alignment to EU states may also have more favorable socioeconomic conditions that facilitate voluntary/incentivized return.

EU candidacy status also yields inconsistent results. While initially associated with 13.4% higher total returns (Model 1) and 28.7% higher forced returns (Model A), these effects vanish with dyad fixed effects. Surprisingly, EU candidacy correlates with lower voluntary/incentivized returns (up to 39.7% decrease). We propose two explanations: First, given shorter distances and cheaper travel costs, EU candidate countries' nationals may be more likely to return without official assistance or enforcement. Unassisted voluntary return is systematically undercounted in the EIL database, representing a major limitation of the data source (Maliepaard et al., 2022). Second, the variable may capture between-country variation rather than causal impact.

Contrary to expectations, economic leverage via trade and aid shows negligible influence. A 1% increase in exports from a third country to the EU is associated with just 0.02% more returns. Aid flows show slightly negative effects: a 1% increase in aid disbursements (in

thousands of US dollars) corresponds to 0.01-0.02% fewer returns. These patterns suggest that material leverage plays a limited role in shaping return cooperation.

Domestic Political and Economic Pressures

Hypothesis 3 receives limited support. Neither economic conditions nor domestic political dynamics consistently predict return outcomes. Effects of GDP growth and unemployment in both origin and destination countries are small (0.5%-1.5% per percentage points change in respective rates) and often switch signs across models (Models 1 and 4).

In modality-specific models, destination-country GDP growth rate is positively associated with forced return (3.4% in Model A, 1.5% in Model C), while unemployment yields contradictory results. Origin-country economic conditions similarly show minor or insignificant effects once dyad fixed effects are added.

Political terror in countries of origin initially correlates with higher returns, supporting the notion that authoritarian regimes may be more amenable to accepting returnees (Stutz & Trauner 2025). However, these relationships lose significance under more restrictive specifications, indicating that the observed effects are largely cross-sectional.

Remittances, contrary to expectations that remittance-dependent countries resist return, are positively correlated with both forced and voluntary returns in baseline models but lose significance once dyad fixed effects are included. This suggests that rather than changes in remittances flows, structural dyadic factors underlie the relationship.

Asylum inflows to EU countries consistently predict lower enforced return. An 1% increase in asylum applications in the prior year is associated with a 0.015-0.05% decrease in

total returns, and 0.085% (forced) and 0.064% (voluntary) decreases in Model A. These findings suggest that rising asylum demand may overburden immigration enforcement systems, thereby constraining return capacity.

Public opinion (i.e., migration salience) and far-right party strength have marginal effects. A one percentage point increase in immigration salience is associated with a small uptick in forced returns (1.2% in Model A, 0.8% in Model C), while far-right parliamentary presence shows no consistent correlation (one percentage point increase corresponds to 1.1% increase in forced return in Model A but not statistically significant in Model C; and 1.3% decrease in voluntary/incentivized return in Model C but only marginally significant in Model A).

Sociocultural and Historical Ties

Hypothesis 4 finds partial support. Colonial history is a strong and consistent predictor of return: dyads with colonial ties show a 13% increase in total returns (Models 1 and 4) and larger effects in modality-specific models (15.5% for forced, 24.6% for voluntary/incentivized return in Model A). These effects persist across specifications, underscoring the continued relevance of historical relationships.

Common language, in contrast, is negatively associated with returns in baseline models but loses significance when country-year fixed effects are added. This suggests that linguistic ties alone do not drive return cooperation.

Diaspora networks, measured as prior-year migrant stock, are weak predictors of return cooperation. A 1% increase in diaspora size predicts only 0.06% more return (Models 1 and 2).

Disaggregated results show similarly small (between 0.03% and 0.07%) increases in both return modalities, hinting at modest, and potentially ambivalent, effects of diasporic networks.

Figure 5a Coefficient plot based on aggregate return data (Model 1 with all variables)

Figure 5b Coefficient plot based on return modalities breakdown data (Model A with all variables)

Table 2a. Regression results with aggregate return data (2009-2024)

DV: Log of absolute number of bilateral returns	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Any readmission related agreement	0.022 (0.020)	0.041† (0.021)		
Migrant stock: third country to EU country (log)	0.056*** (0.007)	0.059*** (0.005)		
Common language	-0.152*** (0.026)	-0.026 (0.032)		
Colonial history	0.131*** (0.022)	0.136*** (0.032)		
Safe origin/third country designation	-0.081*** (0.022)	-0.066** (0.021)		
Aid disbursement gross in thousands (log)	-0.028*** (0.003)	-0.023*** (0.003)		
Trade: Third country to EU country in thousands (log)	0.023*** (0.003)	0.036*** (0.004)		
UN voting divergence	-0.050** (0.018)	-0.181*** (0.050)		
EU country embassy in third country	0.213*** (0.027)	0.153*** (0.019)		
Third country embassy in EU country	0.323*** (0.025)	0.262*** (0.020)		
GDP growth rate, EU country	0.006 (0.005)		-0.007*** (0.001)	
Unemployment rate, EU country	-0.011** (0.004)		0.016*** (0.002)	
Government effectiveness, EU country	0.253*** (0.029)		0.188*** (0.025)	
Asylum applications to EU country (log)	-0.050*** (0.011)		-0.015** (0.005)	
Migration salience, EU country	0.008*** (0.002)		0.001** (0.000)	
Far-right MP share, EU country	0.002 (0.002)		-0.001 (0.001)	
GDP growth rate, third country	0.004** (0.001)			0.001 (0.001)
Unemployment rate, third country	0.003*** (0.001)			-0.005* (0.002)
Remittances as share of GDP, third country	0.025*** (0.001)			0.002 (0.002)
Government effectiveness, third country	0.020			0.074***

DV: Log of absolute number of bilateral returns	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
	(0.019)			(0.018)
Political terror, third country	0.052***			-0.021***
	(0.007)			(0.006)
Visa-free to Schengen	0.068***			0.106***
	(0.014)			(0.028)
EU candidate country	0.134***			-0.003
	(0.018)			(0.027)
Return decisions same year (log)	0.343***	0.344***	0.295***	0.302***
	(0.015)	(0.010)	(0.008)	(0.015)
Return decisions previous year (log)	0.046*	0.015†	0.020**	0.014
	(0.018)	(0.009)	(0.007)	(0.009)
Num.Obs.	49877	49877	49877	49877
Std.Errors	by: time	by: thc_3*time	by: thc_3*time	by: euc_3*time
FE: euc_3*time		X		X
FE: euc_3*thc_3			X	X
FE: thc_3*time		X	X	
FE: time	X			
† p < 0.1, * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001				
Dependent Variable: ln(return count + 1).				
Standard errors in brackets				

Table 2b. Regression results with return modalities breakdown (2014-2023)

DV: Absolute number of returns...	Model A		Model B		Model C		Model D	
	Forced	Voluntary	Forced	Voluntary	Forced	Voluntary	Forced	Voluntary
Any readmission related agreement	0.188***	0.015	0.028	0.016				
	(0.025)	(0.024)	(0.032)	(0.038)				
Migrant stock: third country to EU country (log)	0.069***	0.047***	0.031***	0.053***				
	(0.011)	(0.014)	(0.008)	(0.009)				
Common language	-0.227***	-0.024	0.050	0.168***				
	(0.061)	(0.088)	(0.043)	(0.049)				
Colonial history	0.155***	0.246*	0.173***	0.392***				
	(0.012)	(0.097)	(0.046)	(0.056)				
Safe origin/third country designation	0.056*	0.026	0.043	0.126***				
	(0.025)	(0.034)	(0.028)	(0.028)				
Aid disbursement gross in thousands (log)	-0.008*	-0.024***	-0.014***	0.007				
	(0.004)	(0.006)	(0.004)	(0.005)				
Trade: Third country to EU country in thousands (log)	0.017***	0.005	0.017**	-0.003				
	(0.003)	(0.006)	(0.005)	(0.006)				
UN voting divergence	0.019	-0.166***	0.177*	0.053				
	(0.033)	(0.034)	(0.079)	(0.068)				
EU country embassy in third country	0.145**	0.127**	0.164***	0.112***				
	(0.054)	(0.039)	(0.027)	(0.026)				
Third country embassy in EU country	0.245**	0.435***	0.153***	0.251***				
	(0.078)	(0.033)	(0.029)	(0.032)				
GDP growth rate, EU country	0.034***	0.024			0.015***	0.006		
	(0.008)	(0.018)			(0.004)	(0.004)		
Unemployment rate, EU country	0.018*	-0.040***			-0.018***	0.014*		
	(0.009)	(0.010)			(0.005)	(0.006)		

DV: Absolute number of returns...	Model A		Model B		Model C		Model D	
	Forced	Voluntary	Forced	Voluntary	Forced	Voluntary	Forced	Voluntary
Government effectiveness, EU country	0.229***	0.116			-0.050	0.199**		
	(0.043)	(0.102)			(0.069)	(0.072)		
Asylum applications to EU country (log)	-0.085***	-0.064***			-0.069***	-0.007		
	(0.022)	(0.015)			(0.011)	(0.014)		
Migration salience, EU country	0.012***	0.004			0.008***	-0.005***		
	(0.003)	(0.003)			(0.001)	(0.001)		
Far-right MP share, EU country	0.011***	0.007†			0.000	-0.013***		
	(0.003)	(0.004)			(0.001)	(0.002)		
GDP growth rate, third country	0.009***	0.004†					0.002	-0.002
	(0.002)	(0.002)					(0.002)	(0.002)
Unemployment rate, third country	0.004***	0.001					-0.009**	-0.007
	(0.001)	(0.002)					(0.004)	(0.005)
Remittances as share of GDP, third country	0.016***	0.024***					0.007†	0.001
	(0.002)	(0.002)					(0.004)	(0.004)
Government effectiveness, third country	-0.042	0.143***					0.008	0.043
	(0.026)	(0.032)					(0.041)	(0.045)
Political terror, third country	0.052***	0.158***					-0.012	-0.008
	(0.008)	(0.017)					(0.014)	(0.015)
Visa-free to Schengen	0.090**	0.158***					0.045	0.297***
	(0.033)	(0.030)					(0.049)	(0.067)
EU candidate country	0.287***	-0.122*					0.053	-0.397**
	(0.024)	(0.049)					(0.076)	(0.131)
Return decisions same year (log)	0.344***	0.355***	0.306***	0.338***	0.245***	0.329***	0.281***	0.309***
	(0.028)	(0.034)	(0.015)	(0.015)	(0.014)	(0.015)	(0.019)	(0.022)
Return decisions previous year (log)	0.043	0.047	0.039**	0.034*	0.019	0.028*	0.041**	0.011
	(0.036)	(0.039)	(0.014)	(0.014)	(0.012)	(0.013)	(0.014)	(0.013)

	Model A		Model B		Model C		Model D	
DV: Absolute number of returns...	Forced	Voluntary	Forced	Voluntary	Forced	Voluntary	Forced	Voluntary
Num.Obs.	20699	20699	20699	20699	20699	20699	20699	20699
Std.Errors	by: time	by: time	by: thc_3^time	by: thc_3^time	by: thc_3^time	by: thc_3^time	by: euc_3^time	by: euc_3^time
FE: euc_3^thc_3					X	X	X	X
FE: euc_3^time			X	X			X	X
FE: thc_3^time			X	X	X	X		
FE: time	X	X						
† p < 0.1, * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001								
Standard errors in brackets								

Conclusion

This study examined how structural, political, and relational factors shape enforced return outcomes from EU countries to third countries. Drawing on a novel dyadic dataset of nearly 50,000 observations from 2009 to 2024 and a disaggregated dataset of over 20,000 return events by modality, we developed a series of Pseudo Poisson Maximum Likelihood models with progressively restrictive fixed effects. These models allowed us to isolate the roles of administrative capacity, bilateral relationships, domestic pressures, and sociocultural ties in determining patterns of forced and voluntary return.

Our findings challenge several conventional assumptions underpinning EU return policy. Most notably, we find that return enforcement is driven less by formal policy instruments or domestic political pressures than by long-standing diplomatic infrastructures and bilateral embeddedness. The most consistent and substantial predictor of return outcomes is the presence of embassies, a proxy for institutionalized diplomatic engagement. The presence of a third-

country embassy in the EU is associated with 26-32% more total returns, including 15-24% more forced returns and 25-43% more voluntary/incentivized returns. This underscores the pivotal role of administrative coordination and political will that flows through established diplomatic channels.

Similarly, the deeply rooted, path-dependent relationship of colonial history emerged as a strong and stable predictor of return success across models. Country pairs with colonial ties see 13% higher aggregate returns and even larger effects in modality-specific estimates. In contrast, the presence of a common official language, while often cited in migration literature, shows inconsistent effects, and diaspora size only weakly correlates with return outcomes. Together, these results offer partial support for Hypothesis 4, suggesting that historical ties matter more than contemporary sociocultural integration in shaping enforcement patterns.

In contrast, Hypothesis 1, which emphasized administrative and institutional capacity, receives qualified support. While embassy presence and government effectiveness both matter, they operate through distinct channels. Government effectiveness in EU destination countries is strongly associated with forced returns, reflecting state capacity to implement coercive measures. Conversely, effectiveness in origin countries correlates more with voluntary returns, suggesting that migrants may be more willing to countries with stronger public service delivery or institutional legitimacy.

Strikingly, two formal instruments of EU return policy, readmission agreements and safe country designations, have only modest and inconsistent effects. Readmission agreements correlate with increases in forced returns (~19%) but are insignificant in more saturated models and unrelated to voluntary returns. These findings undermine the assumption that legal

frameworks alone are sufficient to improve enforcement and suggests that institutional enforcement capacity and relational trust are more critical than formal agreements.

Hypothesis 2, which posited that interstate leverage would improve return outcomes, is only partially supported. The most robust predictor in this category is visa-free access to the Schengen zone, which is associated with higher returns, especially voluntary returns. This may reflect (1) migrants departing voluntarily to avoid entry ban, and (2) a broader cooperative relationship and increased willingness to maintain good standing with EU institutions. However, aid and trade flows, often thought to confer bargaining leverage, are essentially uncorrelated with return enforcement. This challenges the assumption that material incentives alone can secure cooperation on return and readmission.

Political alignment, measured via UN voting similarity, shows inconsistent effects across return types. Politically aligned countries are modestly likely to see higher voluntary return, while forced return may occur more frequently between less aligned pairs, possibly reflecting more transactional or strategically motivated enforcement. The divergent effects point to the importance of disaggregating return outcomes by modality and question the usefulness of broad diplomatic alignment as a single predictive indicator.

Hypothesis 3, which focused on domestic political and economic pressures, is largely rejected. Across all models, GDP growth, unemployment, migration salience, and far-right party strength show weak or inconsistent effects on return enforcement. The notable exception is asylum application volume, which negatively correlates with return outcomes, likely reflecting administrative overload. These findings suggest that domestic political pressures have limited

empirical traction in shaping enforcement behavior, especially when compared to dyadic and structural variables.

Collectively, our results indicate that return enforcement is not primarily a function of policy design or domestic demand, but rather of “relation capacity” and historical entanglement. Countries with established diplomatic channels, shared histories, and ongoing cooperation are better positioned to implement both voluntary and forced returns. Formal agreements and domestic political and economic pressures may play a role but are neither necessary nor sufficient for successful enforcement.

Data Limitations and Unexplained Variation

While our analysis demonstrates important patterns in return enforcement, several limitations warrant discussion. The Eurostat Enforcement of Immigration Legislation database has well-documented validity and reliability issues. The rounding of numbers, the absence of cohort identifiers, and inconsistent practices across member states may obscure smaller but substantive effects. What our model captured as weaker statistical relationships may still reflect substantive policy dynamics.

Moreover, our models explain only a portion of the variation in return outcomes, even with extensive fixed effects specifications. This unexplained variation points to omitted variables that the current data fail to capture: domestic events in both origin and destination countries, informal diplomacy between countries, and post-arrival enforcement regime in the EU member states (Leerkes & van Houte, 2020; Marie Borrelli & Lindberg, 2025). Future research with more granular data could disentangle these effects more precisely.

Policy Implications

The policy implications of these findings are far-reaching. Current EU return strategies are premised on the assumption that readmission agreements, conditionality mechanisms, and domestic enforcement capacity will translate into better return outcomes. However, our evidence suggests otherwise. Returns are more likely where relationships are institutionalized, trusted, and historically embedded instead of merely where formal agreements exist.

This means that return cooperation cannot be manufactured overnight. Policymakers should place greater emphasis on diplomatic presence, long-term engagement, and capacity building in partner countries. Likewise, return strategies that emphasize voluntariness may benefit more from investments in public services, reintegration programs, and origin-country institutional strength than from legal pressure or aid conditionality.

This study contributes to the growing body of literature emphasizing the relational and institutional dimensions of migration governance. By leveraging dyadic data, distinguishing between return modalities, and using multi-layered fixed effects, we offer a more granular understanding of what drives variation in return outcomes. However, we recognize this as an important step rather than a definitive answer.

Future research should explore the micro-dynamics of implementation, such as bureaucratic discretion, informal negotiations, and subnational practices within EU member states. In addition, greater attention to non-documented cases (returns that occur outside official channels) and migrant agency (decision-making under pressure or constraint) would deepen our understanding of how return systems function.

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Appendix

Table A1a. Summary statistics of aggregate return data, 2009-2024 (N=49877)

	Unique	Mean	SD	Min	Median	Max
Return enforcement count	422	40.3	487.8	0.0	0.0	60040.0
...log transformed	422	1.0	1.7	0.0	0.0	11.0
Orders to leave same year	857	120.9	800.8	0.0	0.0	63565.0
...log transformed	857	1.6	2.2	0.0	0.0	11.1
Any readmission related agreement	2	0.2	0.4	0.0	0.0	1.0
Safe origin/third country designation	2	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	1.0
Government effectiveness lagged, EU country	389	1.1	0.6	-0.4	1.1	2.2
Government effectiveness lagged, third country	2055	-0.3	0.8	-2.4	-0.5	2.5
EU country embassy in third country	2	0.4	0.5	0.0	0.0	1.0
Third country embassy in EU country	2	0.4	0.5	0.0	0.0	1.0
Aid disbursement gross in thousands lagged	4674	7610.4	43220.2	0.0	0.0	1780470.0
...log transformed	4674	3.1	3.9	0.0	0.0	14.4
Trade: Third country to EU country in thousands lagged	45166	442855.9	2882851.6	0.0	4342.8	167407248.9
...log transformed	45143	7.9	4.4	0.0	8.4	18.9
UN voting divergence lagged	50258	1.5	0.6	0.0	1.5	3.8
Visa-free to Schengen	2	0.2	0.4	0.0	0.0	1.0
EU candidate country	2	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	1.0
GDP growth rate lagged, EU country	389	1.5	4.0	-16.0	1.9	24.6
Unemployment rate lagged, EU country	385	8.6	4.5	2.0	7.4	27.7
Asylum applications to EU country lagged	375	85540.5	220691.7	50.0	12820.0	2887195.0
...log transformed	375	9.6	2.1	3.9	9.5	14.9
Migration salience lagged, EU country	386	12.9	11.1	0.2	10.0	64.2
Far-right MP share lagged, EU country	54	7.0	11.3	0.0	0.0	61.2
GDP growth rate, third country lagged	2060	3.3	5.6	-50.3	3.7	86.8
Unemployment rate, third country lagged	1889	7.8	6.2	0.1	5.6	35.4

	Unique	Mean	SD	Min	Median	Max
Remittances as share of GDP lagged, third country	1867	4.9	6.9	0.0	1.9	49.9
Political terror lagged, third country	5	2.7	1.1	1.0	3.0	5.0
Colonial history	2	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	1.0
Common language	2	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.0	1.0
Migrant stock lagged: third country to EU country	10341	8549.9	56690.3	0.0	96.0	2015004.0
...log transformed	10341	4.7	3.2	0.0	4.6	14.5

Table 1b. Summary statistics of return modalities breakdown data, 2014-2023 (N=20699)

	Unique	Mean	SD	Min	Median	Max
Forced return count	359	12.6	140.3	0.0	0.0	6996.0
...log transformed	359	0.6	1.3	0.0	0.0	8.9
Voluntary/Incentivized return count	359	13.9	272.7	0.0	0.0	19930.0
...log transformed	359	0.6	1.2	0.0	0.0	9.9
Orders to leave same year	517	98.3	614.7	0.0	0.0	22000.0
...log transformed	517	1.4	2.1	0.0	0.0	10.0
Any readmission related agreement	2	0.2	0.4	0.0	0.0	1.0
Safe origin/third country designation	2	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	1.0
Government effectiveness lagged, EU country	161	1.0	0.5	-0.1	1.1	1.9
Government effectiveness lagged, third country	1366	-0.4	0.8	-2.4	-0.4	2.3
EU country embassy in third country	2	0.3	0.5	0.0	0.0	1.0
Third country embassy in EU country	2	0.4	0.5	0.0	0.0	1.0
Aid disbursement gross in thousands lagged	2112	4415.8	27786.8	0.0	0.0	1269010.0
...log transformed	2112	2.7	3.6	0.0	0.0	14.1
Trade: Third country to EU country in thousands lagged	18971	309457.6	1750865.8	0.0	3495.7	88944490.6
...log transformed	18969	7.7	4.3	0.0	8.2	18.3
UN voting divergence lagged	20784	1.5	0.6	0.0	1.5	3.5
Visa-free to Schengen	2	0.2	0.4	0.0	0.0	1.0
EU candidate country	2	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	1.0
GDP growth rate lagged, EU country	161	2.8	3.5	-9.2	2.6	24.6
Unemployment rate lagged, EU country	160	8.2	4.3	2.0	6.9	26.1
Asylum applications to EU country lagged	158	80895.9	146938.1	170.0	12435.0	829745.0
...log transformed	158	9.6	2.0	5.1	9.4	13.6
Migration salience lagged, EU country	161	15.6	12.4	0.2	12.4	64.2

	Unique	Mean	SD	Min	Median	Max
Far-right MP share lagged, EU country	34	8.1	12.2	0.0	2.0	61.2
GDP growth rate, third country lagged	1370	2.9	5.0	-46.1	3.4	63.3
Unemployment rate, third country lagged	1293	7.9	6.2	0.1	5.5	35.4
Remittances received as share of third country GDP (lagged)	1253	5.0	6.8	0.0	2.1	49.9
Political terror lagged, third country	5	2.7	1.1	1.0	3.0	5.0
Colonial history	2	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	1.0
Common language	2	0.1	0.3	0.0	0.0	1.0
Migrant stock lagged: third country to EU country	5059	6726.8	47129.5	0.0	77.0	1614451.0
...log transformed	5059	4.5	3.1	0.0	4.4	14.3